

POLITICAL SCIENCES

PARTNERSHIP DEVELOPMENT OF UKRAINE AND THAILAND

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Abstract

Ukraine became interested in the Kingdom of Thailand, the key country of Southeast Asia, in the pre-war times. Ukraine systematically and thoughtfully develops bilateral relations with Thailand, although not as intensively as with some other states of the world. In the economic dimension, Ukraine still, despite the war, has positive export-import indicators characterized by active trade.

The article presents an overview of the history of the Kingdom of Thailand, which in Thai means "Land of the Free" called Siam until 1949. This is the only state in Southeast Asia that has never been colonized. And this constitutes a source of special pride for the Thais. For centuries, world powers, in particular Great Britain and France, tried to colonize Siam, but thanks to the wise policy of the royal house, the Kingdom managed to preserve its sovereignty.

Moreover, the article analyses home policy and economy of Thailand, as well as its foreign policy and the role in the system of regional security and stability. Special attention is paid to the positive aspects of economic cooperation with Ukraine, as well as an analysis of the Thai leadership position regarding the Russian war against Ukraine.

Keywords: *Thailand, regional security, Ukraine, beloved partnership.*

A particularly advantageous transit geographical location in the very center of mainland Southeast Asia played a significant role in the development of the Kingdom of Thailand. All countries bordering Thailand are forced to use the geographical "windows" of its territory for successful trade with the world. Thailand is surrounded by friendly states, cooperation with which guarantees the secure development of the entire region. In the north and west is Myanmar (Burma), in the north-east - Laos, in the southeast - Cambodia, in the south - Malaysia. Thailand is a maritime state, which has a significant tonnage of the merchant fleet, consisting of 363 merchant ships. According to this indicator, it occupies 28th position in the list of 158 maritime states. The presence of the fleet, as well as the military, provides the country with wide access to the sea, since the mainland is washed by the Gulf of Thailand, the Andaman Sea, the waters of which extend to the Pacific Ocean. Thailand is a beautiful and naturally wealthy country. It has everything: land, sea, exotic islands, rivers and lakes, mountains and valleys, various deposits, coconut plantations and rubber forests, meadows of green grass and rice fields. And the main wealth of this state, in our opinion, is its hardworking people.

The history of this land is quite ancient and full of a significant number of events: wars, confrontations between rulers, constant changes of power, occupation, revolutionary events, military coups, etc. The historical canvas of the Thai-Siamese land begins to weave from the Stone Age, as in many other nationalities. The royal modern dynasty, which dates back to the end of the 18th

century, was formed from the united lands of Siam by Buddha Yodpha Chulalotsi, who founded the Chakri dynasty. After the coronation, he was named King of Siam Rama I. This dynasty rules the Kingdom of Thailand to this day.

Thailand is officially a parliamentary (bicameral) democracy with a constitutional monarchy. National symbols Sala Thai (Thai Pavilion) is an architectural symbol of the country, reflecting the skill of Thai performers. Chang Thai (Thai elephant or *Elephas maximus indicus*) is a symbol of this statehood, which is historically and traditionally associated with Thailand. The national plant is Rachaphruek (*Cassia fistula* Linn), known as the Piper Tree or in English Indian Laburnum.

The institution of monarchy in Thailand is in many ways unique. It not only has more than seven hundred years of history, but also has managed to maintain its relevance in the modern world. The constitutional monarchy, since the proclamation of the first constitution of the Kingdom in 1932, has been deeply respected and serves as a guiding light and the core force of the country, uniting people of different backgrounds and wealth.

The love and respect that the Thai people have for their King stems largely from the moral authority that His Majesty King Bhumibol Adulyadej the Great (died 13 October 2016), as he was called by his people, exemplified in his outstanding personal contact with the people. His son Maha Vajiralongkorn (Thai: มหาวชิราลงกรณ), the only son of King Bhumibol Adulyadej, was born on 28 July 1952 in Bangkok. He was

crowned on 4 May 2019 and is currently the King of Thailand of the Chakri Dynasty.

At the same time, royal rule is based on principles that can be traced back to the history of Thailand as a nation-state. The Thai concept of monarchy dates back to the early 13th century Sukhothai state, which is considered the first independent Thai kingdom.

Thailand is a multi-ethnic country with a population of 64.1 million. Thai, a tonal language with various dialects, is the national and official language. The alphabet was created in 1283 by King Ramkhamhaeng the Great of the Sukhothai Kingdom. Other languages spoken include Chinese and Malay. English, which is a compulsory subject in the secondary school curriculum, must be spoken and understood throughout the country. The currency of Thailand is the baht, which is divided into 100 satangs.

The majority of Thais, over 90 percent, are Buddhists, although other religions such as Islam, Hinduism, Sikhism, and Christianity are also practiced. [1] The constitution does not mention any religion as the national religion and grants complete freedom of religion to all Thai citizens.

When studying the state of development of Thailand, it should be noted that this state has demonstrated to the whole world a decisive breakthrough in economic growth, breaking away from a backward, archaic, agricultural country to a high level of modern technological power. Thailand is the second largest country in Southeast Asia in terms of economic potential with a nominal gross domestic product (GDP) of about 500 billion US dollars. With a free market economy, the Kingdom has a strong domestic market and a growing middle class, and the private sector is the main engine of development. The economy of Thailand is well integrated into the world market, exports account for more than 70 percent of GDP.

Thailand has a strong industrial sector – 40 percent of GDP and a growing services sector – 50 percent, focused on tourism and the financial services industry. Although the country is traditionally agrarian and one of the few environmentally friendly food exporters in the world, the share of the agricultural sector does not exceed 9 percent of the country's GDP. Thailand is a leader in implementing a liberal trade model, in particular with its Asian neighbors. With a favorable strategic location that provides easy access to the Asian market with more than 660 million consumers, the country has the opportunity to play the role of a central unifying link between the relationships of the single market and the production base.

Today, the Kingdom of Thailand is among the 15 most developed countries in the world in terms of its economic development and ranks second among the countries of Southeast Asia. In 2022, Thailand's GDP growth was 2.6%, which was due to exports of goods, private consumption and investment. The country's nominal gross domestic product (GDP) has exceeded US\$500 billion [2].

Exports include industrial products (74%), agricultural products (13%), agro-industrial (8%), mining, etc. (5%). The main export brands are automobiles and

automobile parts, as well as computers and components, jewelry, rubber products, plastic granules, and chemical products. Agricultural products boast such items as natural rubber, rice, tapioca, processed chicken meat, frozen seafood, chilled vegetables and fruits. Sugar, canned goods, and processed products, etc. are also exported [3]. Consequently, the country is one of the world's largest exporters of rice, sugar, and natural rubber. With a free market economy, the Kingdom has a strong domestic market and a strong middle class, and the private sector is the main engine of the country's development. Thailand's economy is well integrated into the world market: exports account for more than 70 percent of the Kingdom's GDP.

Thailand's foreign policy credo can be briefly defined by the slogan: "Looking to the future." This means openness to the world and stable relations of cooperation and mutual understanding with all countries at the bilateral, regional and multilateral levels. A powerful and responsible participant in the international community, Thailand is distinguished by its special influence in regional and international organizations, seeks to play a constructive role in international affairs and confront the challenges facing the world community. Currently, Thailand maintains diplomatic relations with more than 190 countries, and in 90 it has embassies, consulates general and other diplomatic and commercial missions. The country is also interested in the Central Asian market: in 2012, Thailand opened an embassy in the capital of the Republic of Kazakhstan, Astana. Royal Thai Embassy, Astana, Kazakhstan is located on the 16th floor of the Astana Tower Business Center, 12, in Nur-Sultan. This was noted in the book of diplomatic missions in Kazakhstan (Announcement No. 16/ 2563 On the change of working) [4].

Ukraine-Thailand: cooperation. The contractual and legal basis of Ukrainian-Thai relations consists of 19 documents. The key bilateral agreements are: Agreement on the Establishment of Diplomatic Relations (April 30, 1992); Agreement between the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine and the Government of the Kingdom of Thailand on the Establishment of the Intergovernmental Ukrainian-Thai Commission on Bilateral Cooperation (May 3, 2002); Convention between the Government of Ukraine and the Government of the Kingdom of Thailand for the Avoidance of Double Taxation and the Prevention of Fiscal Evasion with respect to Taxes on Income and Property (November 24, 2004); Agreement between the Government of Ukraine and the Government of the Kingdom of Thailand on Air Services (April 17, 2007); Agreement between the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine and the Government of the Kingdom of Thailand on Defense Cooperation (October 12, 2012); Trade Agreement between the Government of Ukraine and the Government of the Kingdom of Thailand (June 5, 2017); Agreement between Ukraine and the Kingdom of Thailand on Mutual Legal Assistance in Criminal Matters (June 5, 2017); Memorandum of Understanding between the Council of Exporters and Investors of Ukraine under the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Ukraine and the Trade Council of Thailand (December 16, 2021), etc. [5]. It is time to

discuss the issue of establishing a free trade zone with the Thai side.

This story would be incomplete if we did not mention the visit of the future King of Thailand, the then Crown Prince, to Ukraine in 1989 [6]. While still the Crown Prince and performing representative functions of the Royal Family, he visited Ukraine on an official visit. It was precisely on May days, 33 years ago, that the then Crown Prince visited Kyiv and Crimea. There was very difficult to find archival photos and documents about this visit. However, through the efforts of archivists, some information was found [6].

In recent years the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Ukraine had developed Ukraine's Asian Strategy and is now implementing it step by step. This is part of our course to open new horizons in the global world, which is not limited to the Euro-Atlantic space. The course to open new horizons, which includes the Asian and African strategies, strengthening partnerships with African and ASEAN countries, is our hidden opportunities that will help strengthen Ukraine's position on the international stage, restore its economic potential, and guarantee the global role that Ukraine deserves.

In the Southeast Asian region, Thailand has been one of Ukraine's main trading partners in recent years. According to state documents – the order of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dated December 27, 2017 No. 1017-r. – Thailand is included in the list of countries that are potentially attractive for most sectors of the Ukrainian economy and can serve as a reference point for the further development of export activities. In particular, according to the results of 2019, Thailand ranked 9th among the 15 countries to which exports of goods from Ukraine increased the most. Thailand also ranked 32nd among countries in terms of the volume of Ukrainian exports in 2019, ahead of a number of Asian and EU countries. The trade turnover between Ukraine and Thailand in 2019 amounted to over 570 million USD, and in 2016 – 608 million USD [5].

Cooperation in recent years has also confirmed that Ukraine and Thailand have significant potential for further development of bilateral trade and economic cooperation. In 2021, the volume of exports of Ukrainian goods due to restrictions caused by the Covid-19 pandemic reached a relatively low level of 224.886 million USD, but there was an increase of 36.7% compared to the same period in 2020. Imports from Thailand increased by 30.1%. Despite Russia's war against Ukraine, in 2021, ferrous metals became the main commodity item, although the share of agricultural exports in the total volume of Ukrainian exports to the Kingdom of Thailand dominated and amounted to 71.9%. Below is extended information on the structure of bilateral trade in 2021: Ukrainian exports amounted to: ferrous metals – 46.3%, \$104.206 million; cereals – 35.3%, \$79.349 million; residues and wastes of the food industry – 5.1%, \$11.573 million; fats and oils of animal or vegetable origin – 3.1%, \$6.899 million; aluminum and products made from it – 1.6%, \$3.617 million; products of the flour and cereal industry – 1.6%, \$3.600 million. Exports of cereals decreased by 27.1% and amounted to 354 thousand

tons of grain. Ukraine's share in Thailand's imports was 0.05% [5].

Ukrainian imports from Thailand consisted mainly of technical equipment: nuclear reactors, boilers, machines – 23.1%, \$58.205 million; electrical machines – 14.7%, \$37.163 million; land transport, except railways – 14.4%, \$36.268 million; rubber, rubber – 13.5%, \$34.175 million; other types of land transport – 10.2%, \$19.779 million; processed products – 6.4%, \$16.213 million; plastics, polymeric materials – 5.2%, \$13.071 million.

According to the State Customs Service of Ukraine, in 2022 the volume of bilateral trade amounted to \$197.671 million: exports – 35.22 million, imports – 162.451 million, with a negative balance of – \$ 127.231 million. The largest import items: passenger cars and other motor vehicles for the transportation of goods; automatic data processing machines and their units; electronic integrated systems; tires; figs. Export nomenclature: starches; sunflower, safflower or cottonseed oils; remote controls, panels, consoles; sugar confectionery without cocoa content; medicinal products dosed or packaged for retail sale; bakery products. In January-May 2023, the trade turnover between Ukraine and Thailand amounted to \$98.425 million (exports – 24.876 million, imports – 73.549 million). The negative balance was \$48.673 million.

At the same time, the Embassy of Ukraine in the Kingdom of Thailand of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Ukraine warns that the Thai is protecting its own market and its own producers in every possible way, removing some provisions related to critical export sectors from the liberal trade scheme. Thus, in 2017, a new version of the "Law on Public Procurement and Supply Management" came into force in the Kingdom of Thailand, which regulates and unifies public procurement mechanisms and the construction sector at the local and national levels. The exceptions to the law are: the sphere of national security (purchase of weapons and service of military equipment), medical equipment, scientific research, procurement for the needs of higher education, etc.

What industrial niches can Ukrainian technologies occupy? As of today, Thailand is in the so-called economic "middle income trap", when the country, having reached an average level of well-being, is unable to continue its growth. At such a moment, there is an urgent need to move to a new growth model, in particular through the development of new technologies with high added value, investments in scientific and educational projects, and institutional reforms. It is in the development and implementation of these tasks that our state could participate, since Thailand pursues a policy of concentrating efforts on the renewal of those industries that have the highest potential for further development.

Therefore, the "Thailand 4.0" plan provides for the concentration of attention and funds of government and business circles on 10 priority areas of industry, which include existing and newly created industries. The first five existing leading areas of the country's economy includes: the development of the next generation of the automotive industry; smart electronics; tourism and medical tourism; agriculture and biotechnology; food

industry. These industries account for about 63% of Thailand's GDP. The new 5 areas of interest to the government include: robotics; aviation and space technologies; bioenergy and biochemistry; digital technologies; medical equipment and healthcare.

In order to attract foreign investment to implement the "Thailand 4.0" plan, the Thai Government is working to create special economic zones, providing all kinds of state support for their full-fledged operation. The main hopes are placed on the special economic zone "Eastern Economic Corridor" (EEC), the Law on which was adopted on May 14, 2018. EEC is an initiative of the Thai Government to introduce a special economic zone for local and foreign entrepreneurs and corporations, to which the government provides tax benefits. The goal of the initiative is to develop a new generation of Thai industry and create products with high added value.

The Eastern Economic Corridor is located on 160,000 hectares, which includes three coastal Thai provinces. Companies that open their enterprises in the territory of the "Eastern Economic Corridor" are provided with tax holidays for up to 15 years. They also have at their disposal all logistics facilities, such as seaports, high-speed railways and highways for the supply of manufactured products, both for export and for the Thai market.

At the same time, in accordance with the "Law on Foreign Business Activities" (1999), foreign companies are prohibited from carrying out activities in the field of construction, engineering, architecture, etc.

Taking into account the high level of Thailand's nominal GDP, the growth of incomes and the stable socio-economic situation in the country, Thailand remains a key partner of Ukraine among the countries of the Southeast Asian region in the long term. Ukraine, with its economic, scientific and technical, agricultural and industrial potential, as well as its geographical location, can be an important partner for Thailand in entering the markets of Eastern Europe and the European Union.

The Ukraine pays attention to the diversification of foreign trade and attracting foreign investment in new areas of cooperation, as well as participation in promising infrastructure projects planned for implementation by the Government of Thailand. In recent years, cooperation between the Chambers of Commerce and Industry of Ukraine and Thailand has been actively developing. On July 20, 2021, a joint meeting of the leadership of the Ukrainian Chamber of Commerce and Industry and the Thai Chamber of Commerce - the Council of Commerce of Thailand was held, where among the issues was holding a business forum with the participation of business circles of both countries.

In order to create further favorable conditions for bilateral trade, a Memorandum of Understanding was signed on December 16, 2021 in Bangkok between the Council of Exporters and Investors under the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Ukraine and the Council of Commerce of Thailand. In cooperation with the Export Promotion Office and the COIN company on February 17, 2022 the webinar "Go to Asia" was organized to

expand the presence of Ukrainian food products in the markets of Thailand, Singapore and Vietnam.

Scientific and technical cooperation has special prospects. In 2008, the Ukrainian Dnipro launch vehicle developed by the Yuzhnoye Design Bureau launched the first Thai Earth observation satellite, THEOS. In 2021, a stable mutually beneficial cooperation was launched between the State Space Agency of Ukraine and the Geo-Informatics and Space Technology Development Agency of Thailand (GISTDA). In the fall of 2020, the ASEAN Center was launched at the Institute of International Relations of Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv. Minister of Foreign Affairs Dmytro Kuleba, who initiated the project, emphasized that for Ukraine, the development of cooperation with ASEAN was a new great opportunity in science and technology, trade, investment, and economic cooperation. Humanitarian ties between our states are also developing with significant support from Ukrainians in Thailand.

The new Ambassador of the Kingdom of Thailand to Ukraine with residence in Warsaw - Chettaphan Maksamphan began work on December 9, 2020. Our countries agreed to hold the third round of political consultations in 2021, as well as the inaugural meeting of the Joint Commission on Trade between the Government of Ukraine and the Government of the Kingdom of Thailand. Ukraine recalls that in accordance with the provisions of the Export Strategy of Ukraine – "Roadmap for Strategic Trade Development" for 2017-21, Thailand was included in the list of countries that are potentially attractive for most sectors of the Ukrainian economy and can serve as a reference point for the further development of export activities.

Ukraine is and will be a state that offers the world added value, builds honest and mutually beneficial relations with other players, and makes a significant contribution to international peace and security, - noted the then Minister of Foreign Affairs of Ukraine D. Kuleba at the ASEAN summit in Cambodia in November 2022. – Russia is a global threat to the security and well-being of all countries in any part of the planet. It is worth mentioning only Russian food blackmail. Thanks to the efforts of Ukraine, the UN, Turkey, and other international partners, it was possible to protect the Black Sea Grain Initiative and prevent the growth of food risks in the countries of the Global South, which are critically dependent on Ukrainian food. Ukrainian grain exports to Southeast Asian countries amount to \$ 1 billion. Therefore, ASEAN states are interested in the uninterrupted operation of the grain corridor, and in the future - in the restoration of full-fledged supplies, which is impossible without the deoccupation of temporarily occupied territories and the victory of Ukraine.

In conclusion, we would like to note the following. Involving Ukrainian business circles in cooperation with Thailand, it is necessary to consider the tough protectionist policy introduced in this country: with the exclusion from foreign trade of several commodity items that are protected by Thai domestic export-import legislation.

Ukraine has come for a favorable promotion of the Thai market of technologies and innovations (weapons too), since the Kingdom is experiencing a “middle-income trap”. This is a rather difficult task in conditions of war on the one hand. So for other reasons and observational analysis – the indicators of trade between Ukraine and Thailand in 2023 during in the active period of the war against our state, given in the article, inspire some hope for the further development of cooperation. In such a situation – a crisis of the middle class – there is an urgent need to move to a new growth model, in particular through the development of new technologies with high added value, investments in scientific and educational projects, and institutional reforms.

It is in the development and implementation of these tasks that our state could take part. At the same time, we should also remind that the Embassy of the Kingdom of Thailand in Ukraine is located, like many other diplomatic missions during the war, in the capital of the Republic of Poland, Warsaw, which has become a kind of trade hub for Ukrainian goods and logistics transit schemes.

In addition, we would propose to initiate Ukraine's participation in the deployment of the special economic zone "Eastern Economic Corridor" (SEC), which will contribute to attracting foreign investment not only for the implementation of the "Thailand 4.0" plan adopted at the highest level. So, for the restoration of the Ukrainian economy destroyed by Russian aggression. Moreover, the Thai side is also interested in such cooperation.

Ukraine's proactive policy in the Global South brings our victory in a full-scale war closer and strengthens Ukraine's military economy.

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Guru (spiritual teacher) Nanak (1469—1539). Today, the Sikh panth — a religious community — has about 22 million members, of whom 83% live in India, 76% of Indian Sikhs live in Punjab.

Sikhism combines the ideas of Hinduism and Islam. Sikhism believes in the equality of all people and rejects discrimination based on caste, religion, or gender. Sikhism is a monotheistic religion. The Sikh God, Wahiguru, is formless, invisible, and timeless. Sikh scriptures begin with the number 1, symbolizing the universality of God. God is omnipresent and limitless (ik onkar). Sikhs believe that before the creation of the world, there was only God and his will (hukam). By the will of God, the entire universe was created.

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